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Abstract: This article talks about watering the grape harvest and how to properly water the crop at different times of the year. As well as the influence of various innovative methods on grapes.

Key words: grapes, watering, plant, water, system, resource, supply, management

How and when to water your vineyards

Currently, there are several radically different approaches to watering grapes. You will be hard-pressed to find two farmers who use the same irrigation schedule throughout the year. Some farmers believe that certain varieties do not require watering at all (as long as there is sufficient rainfall), while others strongly disagree with this opinion. Those farmers who prefer not to irrigate believe that additional water increases the quantity but reduces the quality of the grapes. We cannot agree that the quality of grapes really depends on the volume of water. The thing is that the amount of water directly affects the ratio of acids and sugars in the fruit, which is a critical factor determining the quality of wine. It turns out that the exact amount of water your vineyard requires is determined based on a number of factors, including the amount of rainfall throughout the year, the age of the plants, their stage of development, growth period, growing conditions, variety, and growing technique. According to the World Food Organization, on average, one plant requires from 500 to 1200 mm of water during one season. You must understand that wine grapes require less water than table grapes. However, these are only general rules and you cannot use them without doing your own analysis.

If grown in a dry and hot climate, the lack of water will lead to a decrease in the growth rate and wilting of the plants.

The following stages are the most critical in terms of water availability:

- Stage of shoot formation

At this stage, the plant needs a lot of water to begin development and preparation for the new season. You must understand that in some cases the plant will have enough water, which is located under the surface of the earth. However, in the case of sandy soil, you will need to provide the plant with additional water.

- The period from the formation of inflorescences to the moment of fruiting

This period is the most important, because it is at this moment that the plant may face an acute lack of water. As a result of the resulting stress, the plant simply will not be able to bear all the fruits.

- The period from the moment of ripening until the beginning of fruit formation

At this stage, lack of water may affect the overall size of the fruit.

- Maturation process

According to farmers, active watering of plants during fruit ripening can significantly improve the overall quality of grapes. However, many wine growers avoid watering at this stage. You must understand that using the right watering system requires a wise and proven approach. Over-watering table grapes can ruin your efforts, while wine grapes won't contain the right amount of sugar. If it rains the day before harvest, you should wait at least 3-4 days, allowing the grapes to "dry out". During this time, the plant will be able to restore the correct water balance.

- After harvest

In order to withstand the cold winter, the plant must form a sufficient number of shoots protected by bark. This is why many farmers choose to water their plants after harvest, allowing them to retain their foliage and preventing additional growth.

Experienced farmers say that a clear indication of a lack of water is the curling of leaves and the descent of vines closer to the ground. Other farmers report that water

stress can be identified by spots on the lower leaves. However, such information cannot be used in all cases without exception. Please note that the second wave of stress begins at the moment when the grape leaves curl and wither.

Today, farmers can use the latest solutions and technologies that allow them to gain a complete understanding of the water requirements of a particular variety.

In general, in the case of table varieties, farmers water the plants at least once a week, starting from the moment the canes form. In some cases, a drip irrigation system is used, the holes in which are located at a distance of 50 cm from each other.

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